

AN ANALYSIS: EARLY DIAGNOSIS AND CLASSIFICATION OF PARKINSON'S DISEASE USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

A degenerative neurological ailment that slowly impairs motor capabilities, people with Parkinson's disease (PD) have symptoms for a considerable amount of time. Early diagnosis is crucial and often relies on analyzing electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, alongside other indicators such as handwriting, voice quality, and olfactory impairment. For the purpose of identifying PD at an earlier stage, this study provides a complete examination of various machine learning models. A dataset was sourced by an UCI Repository and includes recordings made by 31 people, 23 of whom had PD. Data preparation methods are utilised, which encompass cleaning, missing value management, SMOTE balancing, and feature selection. A training set and a testing set are subsequently created from a database in a 70:30 ratio. The precision, recall, F1 score, and accuracy are utilized to evaluate MLP, LR, a proposed classifier, among other classification tactics. The results show that compared to other models, the MLP model has the greatest score (99%), recall (98%), accuracy (98.31%), and precision (100%). The outcomes of this research highlight an usefulness of ML methods for PD early detection. Current results represent only the beginning when it comes to potential future research and development directions in this field. Additionally, working along with healthcare providers to verify the model's predictions and incorporate it into clinical practice might lead to real-life uses in detecting and treating PD at an early stage.

Keywords: Parkinson's Disease, Prediction, Comparison, Dataset, Deep Learning.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The primary regulating organ of the human body is the brain. Any minimal injury to any of its components will have severe consequences for other organs; PD is one of its adverse effects. A protracted neurodegenerative disorder, PD is distinguished by the simultaneous presence of motor and on-motor symptoms in a central nervous system. PD's precise causes are unknown and unclear, although it's believed that both inherited and environmental risk factors have a role. PD affects over 10% of patients and is present in at least one first-degree relative. Additionally, individuals with a history of head trauma and pesticide exposure have a higher prevalence of PD; however, smokers have a reduced risk of developing the condition [1]. Primarily damages neurons in a substantia nigra, a region of a midbrain that produces dopamine, resulting in insufficient dopamine release in this area [2]. The first stages of the disease include tremors, difficulties in mobility, and slowness in move execution. Towards the end of the course of PD, anxiety, dementia, and depression are widespread in a patient's psychology. However, emotional disturbance, sleep disturbance and sensory symptoms will become manifest in patients along with a Parkinsonian syndrome[3] [4]. Along with neuro imaging tests, these symptoms play a important role in diagnosing of a typical PD. A purpose of treatment of PD is not about complete recovery, but to some extent it contributes to resolving signs and symptoms [5]. The increasing use of AI algorithms on clinical datasets in the growing field of medical decision support systems (MDSS) leads medical specialists to more accurate diagnoses and treatment selections [6]. IDS performance was upgraded significantly due to new breakthroughs in ML, AI, and statistical learning that have enhanced DSS. Learned artificial intelligence is ineffective, according to a number of studies[7].

Fig.1. Parkinson's disease

A notable similarity exists among ML and data mining, as two processes frequently employ identical methodologies. However, while ML focuses on making predictions by analyzing clinical data for unknown properties that were previously discovered in the training data, data mining is primarily concerned with identifying such properties. Extensively implemented in bioinformatics, ML techniques play a important role in a diagnosis of medical conditions [8]. Classification and prediction algorithms that can keep up with the ever-growing diversity of medical data are in high demand. According to prior research in machine learning, there are a lot of factors that may affect how accurate a categorization system is. The medical field makes use of ML algorithms to examine diagnostic issues and data sets. As a result, healthcare choices and treatments will be enhanced, and costs will be reduced [9].

A. Contribution of study

A main aim of this research is to compare different methods and techniques for comparative analysis and find best performing model. The key contribution of this paper is:

- The UCI Repository was explored for a dataset on Parkinson's disease, which preprocessed for cleaning, check null values, and data balancing.
- A 70:30 split was applied to the dataset, with half going to testing and half to training.
- ML and DL methods were used for model implementation.
- To assess the effectiveness of the approach in identifying PD, calculate the accuracy, f1 score, precision, and recall.
- To compare a model for find a best performing model.

B. Structure of Paper

The following is the outline of the research. **Section 2** provides a literature review that summarizes relevant publications; **Section 3** details the methodology, preprocessing approach, and dataset that were used in this research. **Section 4** details the proposed model's accomplishments, including comparisons to existing methods, and **Section 5** concludes with future research directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Multiple studies have evaluated PD using different criteria. With the present difficulties in subclassifying PD, assessing risk, and predicting prognosis employing speech signal characteristics, this research provides a firm groundwork for using ML to neurodegenerative disorders. This section contains references to a few of them.

In this paper Challa *et al.*, (2017) build upon previous research that exploited non-motor characteristics including RBD and olfactory impairment. The extended study additionally makes use of significant biomarkers. Using a range of cutting-edge ML strategies, our study aims to model this classifier. Using Boosted LR, RF, Bayes Net, and MLP, we created automated diagnostic models. The greatest results have been found using Boosted Logistic Regression, which has an amazing accuracy97.19% and an AUC-ROC98.9%. Consequently, it may be said that these models may be utilised to anticipate PD early on [10].

This paper (Aich *et al.*, (2019) provided a novel method for choosing feature sets by comparing and contrasting performance metrics with other feature sets, including those based on PCA and genetic algorithms. In order to compare the performance indicators, they have employed several categorisation algorithms. They discovered that by using feature sets derived from genetic algorithms, SVM with RBF achieved an accuracy97.57%. Clinicians may differentiate between the PD and healthy groups using just auditory data with this method [11].

In this paper, Agarwal, Chandrayan and Sahu, (2016) presented a practical method for successfully predicting the onset of PD from audio samples by use of an Extreme Learning Machine. The method's performance was evaluated using a trustworthy dataset obtained from the UCI repository. On the training dataset, the suggested method achieves an accuracy of 90.76% and a margin of error of 0.81 MCC when differentiating between healthy and Parkinson diseased subjects. The suggested strategy achieves an accuracy rate of 81.55% when evaluated with a separate dataset that includes individuals with Parkinson's disease. Current methods, including Neural Network and SVM, are compared to our method's performance. The collected findings demonstrate the reliability of the proposed strategy in recognising Parkinson's disease [12].

A comprehensive overview is the objective of this review, Senturk, (2020) of the most up-to-date methods for diagnosing PD using neuroimaging and related analytic techniques. In order to glean insights from patients, the suggested predictive analytics framework combines K-means clustering with Decision Tree. Machine learning approaches provide for a problem-solving process with a low mistake rate. When doing speech data analysis, it is recommended to use data sets retrieved by an UCI ML repository.

Additionally, the suggested technique incorporates normal and Parkinson's patient spiral drawing inputs to get correct findings. By combining image processing (spiral drawing analysis) with other image processing techniques, the hybrid architecture achieves an 83% accuracy rate for its expected output based on Random Forest Classification and confusion matrices[7].

In this paper Chakraborty *et al.*, (2020) The proposed approach can analyse the spiral and wave drawing patterns of both healthy individuals and PD patients. The technique developed for this research makes use of two independent CNNs to examine a patterns of spiral and wave drawing. In addition, the metal classifier employs ensemble voting to train the prediction probabilities, resulting in a weighted forecasting derived by both a spiral and wave sketches. After training on data from 55 patients, the whole model produced an average f1 score of 93.94%, an average recall94%, an average precision93.5%, and an overall accuracy of 93.3% [13].

In this study, Polat, (2019) they provide a new method to detecting PD using speech signal characteristics. Datasets pertaining to PD were sourced by the ML repository at UCI for the sake of this research. Step one of the suggested hybrid machine learning approach is data pre-processing, often known as over-sampling. Step two is categorization. A dataset with two classes is the one pertaining to Parkinson's disease. In the health category, there are 192 entries, but in the disease category, there are 564 records. The distribution of classes in a dataset is skewed. Using the SMOTE approach, this unbalanced dataset is made balanced again. With its mix of SMOTE and RF, the suggested hybrid technique was able to obtain a classification success rate of 94.89%[14].

Table: 1 Comparative Analysis of Early Diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease using various Machine Learning Techniques

Ref	Methodology	Data set	Performance	Limitations & Future Work
Challa et al.	MLP, BayesNet, RF, Boosted LR	Medical data	Accuracy: 97.159%, AUC: 98.9%	Boosted LR provides a best performance for early prediction of PD.
Aich et al. (2019)	Compared PCA with feature sets generated on genetic algorithms.	UCI ML repository	Accuracy: 97.57% (SVM with RBF kernel)	Limited feature sets explored
Agarwal, Chandrayan & Sahu (2016)	Used Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) with speech samples for prediction.	UCI ML repository	Accuracy: 90.76% (training), 81.55% (test)	Lower accuracy on independent dataset
Senturk, 2020	K-means clustering, Decision Tree	UCI ML Voice Data, Spiral Drawing Inputs	83.00%	Lower accuracy compared to other studies, limited exploration of alternative feature extraction techniques
Chakraborty et al. (2020)	Two CNNs for analyzing spiral and wave drawing patterns, ensemble voting for final prediction.	Data of 55 patients	Accuracy: 93.3%, F1 score: 93.94%	Small dataset; limited diversity
Polat, 2019	SMOTE, Random Forest	Parkinson's Disease Dataset (UCI ML)	94.89%	Limited discussion on the impact of SMOTE parameters, potential biases introduced by oversampling technique

A. Research Gaps

Numerous research gaps that need attention are shown by the comparative investigation of early detection of PD using different ML algorithms. While individual studies demonstrate impressive accuracies, there are overarching limitations that suggest areas for further investigation.

Specifically, the reliance on single datasets across multiple studies raises concerns about the generalizability and robustness of the developed models. Subsequent investigations ought to give precedence to external validation on a variety of datasets after evaluate a performance of models in real-world scenarios and augment their applicability to distinct populations.

Lastly, longitudinal studies are needed to track disease progression precisely, considering the nature of Parkinson's disease that could dynamically evolve. In addition, various strategies such as the exploration of other machine learning techniques, ensemble methods and advanced feature engineering approaches might be used to address biases and variability and finally lead to reliable and clinically useful predictive models.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The section details the operational procedures as well as implementation of a multitude of ML models which aid in a determination of an early diagnosis of PD of this research.

A. Problem Statement

PD, an autoimmune disorder distinguished by motor and non-motor manifestations such as tremors, rigidity, and impaired movement control, is initiated by the progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons. In addition to these symptoms, the condition encompasses cognitive deterioration and mood disorders. Over the years, significant progress has been made in a diagnosis and treatment of PD; however, accurate diagnosis remains challenging, particularly during the initial phases, due to the condition's intricate nature. The complexity of its symptoms and the lack of meaningful clinical biomarkers lead to a missed or wrong diagnosis that can delay treatment and individualized patient therapy. As a result, predictive models that manages to make use of ML and DL algorithms to detect and classify PD for the early management of the condition is also getting high attention. In that case, the development of predictive research that will be able to differentiate between the Parkinson's and non-Parkinson's patients should, therefore, drive a personalization of a disease for clearer results and more information on the disease.

B. Methodology

Identification of PD patients is the goal of the proposed technology. This comparative research utilizes a systematic method that consists of data collection from the UCI repository, thorough preprocessing including data cleaning, detection of null values, SMOTE that is necessary for data imbalance correction, and feature selection. Preprocessed data is next splitted into training and testing sets in preparation for an execution of a model. An MLP, KNN, and a modified classifier are all employed in the forecasting of PD. Several performance measures are utilized to evaluate an efficiency and performance of algorithms, including F1-score, Accuracy, Precision, and Recall. The goal of this research is to achieve by using this comprehensive way the most suitable approaches for PD in the early stage.

1. Data Collection

Collecting data is an extremely preliminary stage in this implementation. The dataset pertaining to PD utilised in this investigation was obtained by the UCI Repository. 23 of an individual in this dataset have been diagnosed with PD, and their biomedical vocal measurements are diverse in nature. the data flow in various steps and phase.

The data flow diagram given below

Fig.2. Flowchart of Parkinson's Disease Detection

2. Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is a crucial phase in implementation, involving the transformation of raw data before feeding it into the designated algorithm. This step aims to convert the raw data into a refined and processed format, enhancing its usability for analysis. The primary objective of data preprocessing is to attain clearer results in a standardized format. Additionally, it facilitates the modification of data to enable the utilization of multiple algorithms during processing and implementation, ensuring adaptability and efficiency in data analysis.

- **Data Cleaning:** Data cleansing entails calculating values in a filled manner while excluding missing values.
- **Check the null value:** The `is null ()` method in Pandas may be used to find null values inside a dataset. This tool helps to identify missing data in fields or columns.

Data balancing with SMOTE: This generic classification model has a problem with its dataset's label distribution. Due to under-fitting or bad model outputs, models built from imbalanced data will provide prediction results that favour brands with samples that span many categories [15]. The SMOTE approach was used to remedy the data imbalance by enhancing a performance of a classification model and balancing a sample sizes across categories.

Feature Selection: This method reduces training time and aids in data cleansing by selecting characteristics based on their highest score. Feature selection is picking out the most important characteristics that have an effect on the dependent variable, either by hand or automatically. The model's performance might be negatively affected by irrelevant features.

3. Data Splitting

To implement the model effectively, a data is divided into training and testing sets. A model is trained exclusively on a training data to learn patterns, while a testing data is reserved for evaluating its performance on unseen examples. The dataset is divided into a 70:30 train/test split in this case.

4. Classification Algorithm

For model implementation, utilize machine and deep learning techniques. In this study, adopt an MLP, RF, DNN, XGBoost, and Proposed classifier for early detection of PD, as described below.

a). MLP (Multilayer Perceptron)

Neurons are the building blocks of a neural network. They communicate with one another via unidirectional connections with varying weights [16]. This study makes use of a FFNN, often called an MLP, which has many hidden layers and an input-output layer. Every MLP layer takes an input vector with D dimensions and returns an output vector with N dimensions.

$$f(x) = \Phi\left(\sum_j w_j x_j + b \dots (1)\right)$$

where x_j , w_j , b , and Φ represent the neuron's inputs, weights, and bias, respectively, and the nonlinear activation function. While training, back-propagation [36] is utilized to change a neuron's parameters in order to minimize an error.

$$w_{new} = w_{old} + \eta XY \dots (2)$$

where η represents the learning rate, denoting the frequency of weight updates throughout the training process. A number of hidden layers (HM) and neurons (NM) at every hidden layer depends heavily on the dataset, making it exceedingly unclear to approximate these values. Adding additional layers and neurons increases a number of parameters, which in turn increases a number of variables that cannot ensure greater performance. Sample size in the training dataset is directly proportional to the number of parameters.

b). Logistic regression (LR)

The major goal of using logistic regression on the categorisation results was to determine the first screening for illness diagnosis and prediction [17]. A two-way binary classification is often solved using LR variables.

5. Performance Evaluation

Performance of classifiers is assessed through evaluation metrics. In order to assess an efficacy of algorithms designed for the prediction of PD, a multitude of performance parameters were applied. Utilise F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision to assess a model.

6. Proposed Algorithm

The proposed algorithm utilised in a development of a system for early detection of PD prediction is described in this section.

Proposed Algorithm: for Parkinson's disease prediction

Step 1: Data Collection

- Collect the Parkinson's Disease dataset by an UCI repository.

Step 2: Data Preprocessing for data cleaning and remove the null value.

Step 3: Data Balancing with SMOTE

Step 4: Feature Selection

- To select a best feature of the dataset, use feature importance.

Step 4: Data Splitting

- Divide a data into training and testing (70:30).

Step 5: apply Classification Model

Step 6: Model Training

- Make use of preprocessed data for model training.

Step 7: Model Evaluation

- F1-score, Accuracy, Precision, and Recall are key performance metrics to consider.

Step 8: Predict Outcome

Finish!!!

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

An outline of the results obtained from the evaluation of the dataset used in this research, including the statistics and classifier performance, will be presented in this section.

A. Dataset Description

Dataset obtained by an UCI ML Repository constitutes the initial step of this approach. Thirteen people (23 with PD) provided a range of biological voice measures. Every individual cell in the table corresponds to a distinct voice measure from the 195 voices that were recorded from the aforementioned individuals ("name" column). In accordance with the values of the "status" column (0 represents health and 1 represents PD), a primary goal of a data is to differentiate among healthy and PD patients.

1. EDA (Exploratory Data Analysis)

Exploratory data analysis is an essential procedure that entails conducting preliminary inquiries on data in order to identify patterns and anomalies for the purpose of testing hypotheses using graphical representations and summary statistics. It is a technique for examining the various types of data utilised by the model. EDA tools enable the execution of particular statistical operations and methods, such as multivariate visualization, univariate visualization, and bivariate visualization.

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Fig3. Heat map for checking correlated columns

Figure 3 illustrates the heat map utilised to identify correlated columns within the Parkinson dataset. In this context, each cell in the heat map represents the correlation coefficient between two columns in the dataset.

2. Performance Measures

Metrics for assessing the efficacy of a model are available for calculation. A critical characteristic of evaluation metrics is their capacity to distinguish between model outcomes. The suggested Parkinson's disease algorithm in this research will be assessed using the confusion matrix, f1 score, accuracy, precision, and recall.

a). Confusion Matrix

Columns in a confusion matrix denote predicted class occurrences, whereas rows in the matrix represent actual class instances. Positives (TP), negatives (TN), false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) are a four potential outcomes.

Fig.4. Representation class of Confusion Matrix

- **True Negative (TN):** The sum of all occurrences that were accurately labelled as belonging to the negative category.
- **True Positive (TP):** A calculation based on how many cases were correctly classified as positive.
- **False Positive (FP):** A count of occurrences that are erroneously classified as positive.
- **False Negative (FN):** A quantity of instances misclassified as negative despite belonging to the target class.

b. Accuracy

The probability that an accurate diagnostic examination will be conducted. The overall efficacy of the classification system is denoted by accuracy. It is supplied as-

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + Fp + TN + FN} \dots\dots (3)$$

c. Precision

One could conceptualize the precision of a classifier as a measure of its accuracy. It is determined by dividing the total number of TP and FP for each class by the number of TP. It is stated as

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \dots\dots (4)$$

d. Recall/Sensitivity

is a metric used to assess the comprehensiveness of a classifier; it quantifies its ability to find every positive occurrence. In mathematical notation, it is expressed as

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

e. F1 score

This refers to a harmonic mean's recall and precision. It accounts for false negatives as well as false positives. It is stated mathematically as:

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2(Precision * Recall)}{Precision + Recall} \dots\dots (6)$$

B. Comparative Analysis

According to f1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall, this section compares a results of many ML and DL performances.

Table: III. Comparative Results of Various ML Model

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
MLP	98.31	100	98	99
LR[18]	70	55	62.5	55

Fig.5. Comparison of model’s performance based on Accuracy

A bar graph representing a model's performance according to accuracy is displayed in Figure 5. An MLP model outperforms compare to other models and achieve 98.31% accuracy. The LR model achieve lowest performance is 70%

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Fig.6. Comparison of model's performance based on Precision

An above figure 6 displays a Comparison of a model's performance based on Precision. An MLP model gives the highest precision of 100%, KNN precision is 99, and LR has achieve the lowest precision score is 55%.

Fig.7. Recall Comparison of models

Figure 7 shows the results of comparing a model's performance based on recall. An MLP model gives a highest recall value of 98% and LR achieve 62.5 recall score. These outcomes demonstrate the different models perform.

Fig.8. F1 Score Comparison of different models

Figure 8 displays a comparison of F1 scores for several models. An MLP model gives a highest f1 score of 99%. The KNN model also exhibits the highest f1-score is 92%. The LR model's F1 score of 55% suggests that it performs quite poorly.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Parkinson's disease sufferers are becoming more and more numerous at a startling pace. As such, there is a greater need to concentrate on this disease's diagnosis. Since a diagnosis of PD is non-directed, it cannot be made using the existing diagnostic techniques, such as an ECG or blood test. Clinicians customarily peruse the patient's medical records prior to concluding a comprehensive neurological examination. The findings of published research utilizing ML for the identification and differentiation of PD are summarized in this research. A dataset on PD was obtained by an UCI Repository and includes biomedical voice measures taken from both PD patients and healthy controls. Data cleaning, null value handling, and using SMOTE for data balancing were all parts of the data preprocessing. The dataset was subsequently partitioned 70:30 to separate a training dataset and a testing dataset. An early detection of PD was facilitated by the different machine learning architectures utilized, eg, MLP, KNN. F1 score, recall, accuracy, and precision were among the several measures used to evaluate the model's efficacy. The MLP model that exhibited 98.31% accuracy, 100% precision, 98% recall and 99% F1 score is a best model under these models. Unable to show evidence of the robustness of the study with larger datasets and higher diversity population constitutes one of the two main weaknesses. It is anticipated that the model is likely to generalize well to the real-world scenarios as well as the enhancements of the robustness of the model are the areas of future work.

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